

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399843>

SHORT NOTES / BREVI NOTE

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UPDATE TO THE DISTRIBUTION OF *MELITAEA AETHERIE* (HÜBNER, [1826]) (*Lepidoptera Nymphalidae*) IN SICILY

Aggiornamento della distribuzione di Melitaea aetherie (Hübner, [1826]) (*Lepidoptera Nymphalidae*)
in Sicilia

Melitaea aetherie (Hübner, [1826]) is a species of Nymphalidae with an Atlantic-Mediterranean distribution, of which colonies are known in Morocco (TARRIER, 2001), Algeria and Tunisia (TEN-NENT, 1996). It is found also in Sicily (ROMANO, 1967; CERNIGLIARO *et al.*, 1988) and in Calabria, peninsular Italy (SCALERCIO, 2003). It is considered highly localized in Italy and vulnerable (JUTZELER *et al.*, 2004; BALLETO *et al.*, 2007, 2014; www.iucn.it). In Sicily, it was known since the early '800, when it was first reported by TREITSCHKE(1834) upon collections made in the island by Dahl, a very active entomological collector at the time. Reported by various following authors (e. g. RAGUSA, 1889, 1916-1919), all recent publications report the species mostly from the mountains complex of the northern and western part of the island (Madonie, Nebrodi and Sicani), always inland, at hill-side or uplands, with only one station near the coast, on the lowland south of Agrigento (Valle dei Templi), one station in the centre of Sicily (Pergusa, Enna) and one in the south-east of the region, at Grammichele (Catania province, not Siracusa as reported in literature) (JUTZELER *et al.*, 2004; INFUSINO & SCALERCIO, 2011) (Fig. 1). During this study, the species was recorded in several new stations, most of which along the coast or at low altitudes. Observations were conducted during March-June 2010-2023, in the provinces of Siracusa and Ragusa, where monitoring of the local fauna was regular and continuous. All the Nature Reserves and protected areas were monitored in spring, but also most of the territory of faunistic relevance was checked during zoological researches. In the Fig. 1, the black square indicates the formerly known distribution sites derived from literature (JUTZELER *et al.*, 2004; INFUSINO & SCALERCIO, 2011), while the black star indicates the new records obtained in 2010-2023. All the observations were made from sea level up to 408m a.s.l. In total, the species was observed in ten new localities within nine 10 x 10 km squares of the regional territory (Tab.1; Fig. 1). All the recorded localities are in the province of Siracusa (south-east Sicily). No specimens were collected, due to its vulnerable status, only photographs were taken (Fig. 2). First imagoes in flight were observed by 25th March, with last observed by 2nd June. No more than 10 adults were counted per day/per site, with an average of 3 per day/site. The maximum numbers were recorded along the coast of Siracusa at Penisola della Maddalena – Capo Murro di Porco (37°1'45.02"N, 15°18'57.44"E; 37°0'14.37"N, 15°20'2.74"E) and at Saline di Morghella (36°42'19.34"N, 15°7'10.11"E). New records were not previously reported (JUTZELER *et al.*, 2004;

Fig. 1 — Known (black squares) and new (black star, this study) distribution sites of *Melitaea aetherie* (Hübner, [1826]) in Sicily. The sites where the species was found during this study more frequently and with higher number, are shown with bigger stars.

Fig. 2 — Imago of *Melitaea aetherie* (Hübner, [1826]) photographed at Capo Murro di Porco (Siracusa, Sicily) on 29th April 2015 (Brian J. Small).

Tab. 1. Localities, meters above sea level, GPS coordinates (N,E) and frequency of observation of *Melitaea aetherie* (Hübner, [1826]).

LOCALITY	M A.S.L.	NORTH	EAST	FREQUENCY OF RECORDS
PENISOLA DELLA MADDALENA	18m	37°0'14.37"	15°20'2.74"	REGULAR
MASSA OLIVIERI	0m	37°1'45.02"	15°18'57.44"	REGULAR
SALINE DI MORGHELLA	6m	36°42'19.34"	15°7'10.11"	REGULAR
COSTA DI MORGHELLA	25m	36°42'54.80"	15°6'47.30"	REGULAR
VENDICARI (various sites)	13m	36°49'2.09"	15°6'22.14"	REGULAR
PENISOLA MANGHISI – THAPSOS	11m	37°9'1.35"	15°14'11.64"	SCATTERED
PRIOLO GARGALLO	55m	37°8'10.92"	15°11'38.17"	SCATTERED
ANAKTORON PANTALICA (SORTINO)	408m	37°8'10.24"	15°1'38.66"	SCATTERED
CAPO PASSERO	8m	36°40'16.77"	15°7'53.85"	SCATTERED
COSTA SIRACUSA MAZZARRONA	18m	37°6'20.75"	15°17'35.82"	SCATTERED

INFUSINO & SCALERCIO, 2011). Particularly interesting is that most of the observations were made on lowlands and along the coast, in the arid-semi-steppic habitat just along the coastline or in wetlands (old salt-pans and marshes); in all cases, the area was extensively covered with *Carduus crispus* (L., 1753) and chiefly by *Galactites tomentosa* Moench, 1794. These observations increase of about double the number of localities where the species it is found in Sicily, changing the knowledge of its distribution. It is now clear in fact that *M. aetherie* is much more widespread than until now believed. However, its populations are overall rather scarce, with sparse and loose little nuclei all over its distribution area, being always and everywhere found with small numbers. It remains therefore an endangered species, chiefly due to the steppic, semi-steppic and often arid or marginal habitat

inhabited, that are disappearing all over Europe and in danger for the climate changing and agricultural technology. Certainly, it is one of the least encountered butterflies of Sicily, hard to see and always scarce.

Acknowledgments — I warmly thanks Brian J. Small and David Fairhurst for the help in the field during finding and photographing of the species. Dr. Alberto Zilli is warmly thanked for the help with references.

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